

Abdulla Avloniy's Views on Culture and History

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Abstract:

As Uzbekistan gained its independence, a new era in its spiritual life began - a phase of spiritual cleansing and awakening. "Today we have a historic opportunity to critically evaluate our paths, identify the foundations of our national statehood, return to the roots of our great culture, the roots of our ancient heritage, and apply our rich traditions from the past to the construction of new societies. The need for faith " is also reflected in the principles of " Strategy of Action for the Five Priorities of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 " aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance.

Keywords: historic opportunity, Abdulla Avloniy, Culture and History, madrasah, independence,

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Introduction

At the beginning of the 20th century, the name of Abdulla Avloniy, one of the prominent figures in the field of science, education and culture, was a prominent figure. This is because the efforts of the person, the articles published in the national press, and his published works have, in a literal sense, served the nation's prosperity and are still relevant today.

Abdulla Avloniy was born on July 12, 1878, in the Mergancha neighbourhood of Shaykhantahur district of Tashkent in a family of ordinary weavers. He was educated in a regular school, and at the age of 12, he entered the madrasah. He began to write poems from 1894, as Avloni's autobiography says. Avloniy went on to become acquainted with newspapers and magazines published in different cities of Russia, which were news of that time. Abdulla Avloniy's Views on Culture and History.

MAIN BODY

As Uzbekistan gained its independence, a new era in its spiritual life began - a phase of spiritual cleansing and awakening. "Today we have a historic opportunity to critically evaluate our paths, identify the foundations of our national statehood, return to the roots of our great culture, the roots of our ancient heritage, and apply our rich traditions from the past to the construction of new societies. The need for faith " is also reflected in the principles of "Strategy of Action for the Five Priorities of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 " aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance.

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readers of the newspaper were called "Mullah" by the Mullah. Abdulla Avloniy also joined the Jadid movement since 1904.

More than a dozen books written by Abdulla Avloniy from 1909 to 1917 for special school children were published around the world. His textbooks, such as "The First Teacher", "The Second Teacher", "The Turkish Gulistan or Morality", "School Guild" served as a textbook for the new method schools.

As is well known, one of the most famous works of Abdulla Avloni, sealing his name in history pages, is the Turkish book Gulistan or Ethics, published in 1914. He was highly regarded by his contemporaries and even mentioned in Soviet literature. The newspaper Sadoi Turkiston writes in the headline "Great Turkestan " and reads "... The long-awaited Turkestan ethical book" Turkestan Gulistan "in the open language, by Abdulla in Turkestan An important piece of 132 pages, written by Avloni, printed on stone, was published. The main purpose of his writings was the ethical interpretation of the issue of education. He views morality as a science that calls people for good and prohibits evil. Abdulla Avloniy, in his work, refers to the word ignorance - claiming that it is unreadable, uneducated and ignorant.

According to Abdulla Avloni, everyone should make changes in their everyday lives. After all, talking about culture and progress to people who are not wealthy and do not give it the expected results. First and foremost, economic culture should be developed. Because, "courage in today's world is rich in wealth, which state and state are the dominant one. Because, for the government, the people, skills for the people, knowledge for the profession, money for knowledge are needed. According to him, the time when "our grandparents would be great or not" is over, and the time has come to replace it with "know and does not know." Americans sow one wheat, get twenty packs of wheat, and the Europeans bring us five cents of cotton and sell it for twenty-five kopecks. But we Asians, especially Turkestans sell dumplings, chew candles, give sour cream, milk, and bite on bread. In short, to be modern, it requires economics, honesty, endless effort and endless effort to equip people with science and education. He encourages them to take rhyme and sees the cause of dependency relentlessly.

One of the positive things that the author draws attention to is the Hafzi, that is, the issue of language. The progressive intelligentsia of that time repeatedly emphasized in the press that the language is as important as water and air to help indigenous children take their place in society, and become professionals who care for their motherland and nation. When it comes to language, we must remember our grandfather A. Navoi. "Why shouldn't the Turkish be so Persian, as it has become more affluent with the Persian language? There are so many

beautiful works in Persia, and if their system is not understood by the Turkish, why should they be deprived of it and remain in such a state that it cannot be used." From this, we can see just how much our grandfather was passionate about his language and wanted to spread it around the world.

Abdulla Avloniy says that "every nation has its own language and literature is not preserved" and it is called "linguistic protection." It is the language and literature of life that reflects the existence of every nation in the world. The loss of the national language, he argues, is the loss of the nation's spirit.

Another important feature of Avloni is her journalistic career. His Shukhrat and Asia newspapers have been published for a short time under his editorship. In the newspaper Sadoi Turkistan, Avloniy shared a pen with the pseudonym "Indamas". Avloniy addressed to young people in terms of culture: "a glittering, shivering pants, wearing a European cap," culture! " "It is a culture of ridicule, ridicule, a little bit of Muslim or semi-Russian," he said. Abdulla Avloniy divides the symbol of true culture into three parts: science, domestic life and morality. Naturally, these directions are vital components in the upbringing of the present and future generations, and we can learn how great our ancestors were.

The theatre was a great event in Turkestan cultural and educational life. At the same time, theatre is not only a place of spiritual education but also a major source of material support for the education sector. That is why the progressives have been trying hard to develop national theatre

During this period, amateur theatre lovers had the opportunity to develop their own creative and troupe activities. In 1913, after the "Padarkush" new works in national playwriting were created. Among them was the repertoire of the plays by Abdulla Kadiri, such as "The Unhappy Groom", Abdullah Avloniy's "Easy to Advocate", "Pinak" and "Mazluma's Wife" by Hoji Moin. These theatres are based on the troubles of life at that time and are mainly portrayed by a spectacular audience. When we analyze Abdullah Avloniy's article "Discussing Theater," the writer tries to explain to young people what theatre is in simple terms. According to the author, "theatre is an idle game to eradicate the evil traditions and customs of every nation." Thus, in the eyes of the theatre industry, first of all, it was a "great school", a "temple", and promoted such ideas as education and knowledge, such as schools and the press. From 1921 to 1930 Abdulla Avloniy worked at various educational institutions. Abdulla Avloniy was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor" in 1927 and "People's Artist of Uzbekistan" in 1930. The untimely death has put an end to his intense activity.

CONCLUSION

In general, all the noble deeds of Abdulla Avloniy during his lifetime, including all articles written by ordinary people, contributed to the development of tomorrow.

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